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INTENTIONAL EXCITATION OF A RADIAL TURBINE ROTOR BY MEANS OF GEOMETRICAL MISTUNING OF THE VANE RING

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that the excitation of Low-Engine-Orders (LEO) can lead to failure of turbomachinery components due to High-Cycle-Fatigue (HCF). To ensure the mechanical integrity, one possibility is to reduce this kind of excitation or increase the total damping. LEO predominantly stems from non-uniform inflow conditions, manufacturing tolerances, deposits or wear. In previous investigations it was shown that high-fidelity CFD simulations can enhance the knowledge of such excitation phenomena and can accurately predict the induced forcing patterns. A combination of powerful and reliable Finite Element (FE) and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations can be used to predict the resulting stresses and strains at resonance conditions reliably. Although the numerical effort for such forced response simulations is still high, it is possible to reduce simulation costs while not compromising in prediction accuracy. On the structural side, mode-superposition may be used for example. With this method, it is possible to use the natural frequencies and mode shapes from a prestressed modal analysis, to characterize the dynamic response from harmonic excitations. On the aerodynamic side, the computational costs can for example be cut down by the use of frequency domain methods, such as the Non-Linear Harmonic (NLH) method. The present paper will demonstrate in-

tentional excitation of a radial turbine by employing mistuned upstream inlet guide vanes (IGV). The reason for doing so lies in the objective to study LEO phenomena in this turbine. By intentionally modifying the cross-sections of the vane ring, a specific engine order may be induced. The magnitude of the LEO excitation can be tailored to the specific needs. The simulation methodology is validated by means of test data using a turbine featuring such a mistuned vane ring. Besides the detailed modeling process of the mistuned IGV, the strains and stresses of the resonance crossings of induced engine orders and the corresponding modes from a structural model will be compared.

NOMENCLATURE

A	area (m ²)
E	energy (J)
f	frequency (Hz)
\underline{h}	complex displacement (m)
\underline{p}	complex pressure (Pa)
r	radial coordinate (m)
S	scaling factor (-)
\underline{W}	complex work (W)

Greek Symbols

π	circle number (-)
ζ	damping ratio (-)

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Subscripts

cycle	per cycle
blade	over the blade
aero	aerodynamic
kin	kinetic
max	maximum

Abbreviations

BM1	Fundamental bending mode
BTT	Blade-Tip-Timing
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
FRA	Forced Response Analysis
FE	Finite Elemente
HCF	High-Cycle-Fatigue
IBPA	Inter-Blade-Phase-Angle
IGV	Inlet Guide Vane
LE	Leading Edge
LEO	Low-Engine-Order
ND	Nodal Diameter
NLH	Non-Linear-Harmonic
SG	Strain Gauge
TE	Trailing Edge
TWM	Traveling Wave Mode

BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

Since the worldwide need for energy is increasing, the demand for the development of associated machinery for power generation is high. Besides the continuous expansion of the use of renewable energy, the increase of efficiency of the widely used mechanisms is the main target of current days. This rise can for example be reached by boosting the power-to-weight ratio due to the decreasing material use. Vice versa, this means that the parts of the employed machines have to become lightweight compared to the present products while not compromising in performance. To cover this, it is necessary to get a deeper knowledge of physics in the separate components to reduce the security factors and subsequently the mass.

In this context, turbomachinery is constantly under development because it still plays a vital role in the supply of electricity. But the trend toward slender rotor wheels is leading to higher mechanical blade loading and hence to HCF. Especially LEO is dangerous because of the concurring resonance conditions occurring at high speeds with fundamental blade modes that exhibit higher vibration levels. Therefore, there are a lot of different investigations concerning forced response prediction and in particular, the LEO excitation are published during the past years. Some of them are summarized in the following.

According to Breard et al. [1], inherent non-uniform spacing of the stator blades, flow exit angle variations, axial gap

changes between the rotor and stator blades, general unsteadiness through the engine, density variation due to combustion effects, blade numbers through several stages and effects due to burner variability are the most significant LEO excitation sources. They have investigated the influence of the given parameters on the forcing of the rotor in an axial HP turbine stage and found that it appears that the amount of perturbation in a change of specific excitation sources is proportional to the excitation itself.

Netzhammer et al. [2] have investigated the excitation due to a vaneless asymmetrical volute of a radial turbine. The influence of the volute tongue position in terms of distance to the rotor inlet and the circumferential tongue angle have been examined particularly. The outcome is if the rotor inlet is getting closer to the tongue position the higher the forcing of the investigated LEO is. Considering the effect of the tongue angle, the higher the defined angle the lower the excitation.

Similar to the content of the present work, the low engine excitation due to a mistuned stator of an axial turbine was investigated by Vahdati et al. in [3]. Contrary to the intentional excitation described in this paper, a well-defined pattern was used to create a throat width variation without concerning the overall throughflow area. The circumstance that the unsteady aerodynamic forcing is increasing in magnitude with the scale of the scatter in throat width variation is one of the main findings of the authors.

The influence of detailing for forced response prediction of a transonic axial turbine stage featuring a split nozzle ring was examined by Müller et al. in [4]. The authors described the design process of the associated structure as well as the throughflow models as crucial for the correct prediction of induced strains and stresses. The comparison of numerically predicted and measured strains shows small differences and the discrepancy could be explained by the overestimation of the damping during the measurement and mistuning which was not accounted for in the simulations. Moreover, it has been shown that the level of detailing might have a considerable effect on the prediction accuracy necessitating diligent convergence studies.

As the prediction of LEO excitation remains a challenging task, the test case presented in this paper allows studying the phenomenon in a controlled and detailed manner by employing an intentionally mistuned vane ring.

PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATIONS

The current test case comprises a radial turbine for marine applications that also has been investigated in previous studies [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. This turbine features a single scroll volute, an upstream stator with 24 equally-spaced vanes (baseline geometry) and an integral rotor with 12 blades. To study the steady and unsteady aerodynamics, various CFD models have

been used in this study. At first, the overall performance of the turbine is simulated using the model depicted in Fig. 1(a), comprising the inlet volute and periodic sectors of the stator and rotor respectively, including the backspace and the scallop. This model comprises 7.5 million hexahedral cells. Secondly, a model of the isolated rotor as shown in Fig. 1(b) is used to predict the aerodynamic damping. This model comprises 2.1 million hexahedral cells while resolving details such as the backspace and the scallop. To ensure the correct operating conditions of the isolated rotor model, inlet conditions are iteratively adjusted until the blade loading matches the one from a full-stage simulation within 1% accuracy. In the aerodynamic damping simulations, the blade motion obtained from a prestressed modal analysis is applied as moving mesh boundary condition, as described in Buchwald et al. [10]. The third model shows the model used for the investigation of the mistuned vane ring, see Fig. 1(c). This model comprises a full-annulus version of the vane ring in which each blade is destaggered according to an intended pattern while the other components such as the volute and the detailed rotor are reused from the baseline model. However, the stator is modeled as full annulus and each stator blade position is changed following the designed mistuning pattern. In total, this leads to a high number of 17.4 million elements.

The turbine performance characteristics used to determine the best efficiency points are computed from a series of steady RANS simulations. These simulation results are furthermore used as initial solutions for the unsteady aerodynamic simulations. At the inlet, total pressure, total temperature and the turbulent viscosity are set as constant boundary conditions and the flow is entering the domain normal to the inlet. At the outlet, the averaged static pressure is set as boundary condition. To reach different operating points, the pressure and temperature boundary conditions are derived from test data. The one-equation Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model is used for all simulations in this study since it has proven to be robust and accurate, see [5]. The walls are treated as adiabatic featuring non-slip conditions while the fluid is modeled as perfect air.

As Kovachev et al. describe in [5], the NLH multi-rank approach is appropriate to accurately predict the aerodynamic forcing by resolving the first three fundamental frequencies. For the aerodynamic damping simulations, it is sufficient to solely include the frequency of the mode of interest. The same modeling approach is used in this study.

The FE model of the rotor used to compute the structural behavior is shown in Fig. 2. This model comprises a periodic sector of the turbine rotor. While the hub is modeled using an unstructured mesh with tetrahedral elements, structured meshes with hexahedral SOLID186 elements are used for the blade and the stub shaft. Overall the mesh consists of 392620 nodes with 118832 elements. All FE simulation are carried out with the stub shaft clamped. The natural frequencies of the

(a) Numerical model of the radial turbine stage

(b) Numerical model for damping calculations

(c) Numerical model with mistuned stator

FIGURE 1. CFD models

turbine rotor are determined from a pre-stressed modal analysis. The temperature dependency of the Young's modulus is accounted for using the respective mean blade temperature obtained from steady CFD simulations as input. Finally, the forced response analysis is carried out using the mode superposition method and the aerodynamic forcing obtained from unsteady CFD simulations.

FIGURE 2. FE model

Nakos et al. [11] showed a way of reducing the flow-induced vibrations by mistuning the rotating part of the examined turbine. This reduction has exemplarily been demonstrated on the fundamental bending mode (BM1), which necessitated the simulation of the aerodynamic damping behavior at the corresponding resonance conditions. The respective rotational speeds were determined from the SAFE diagram depicted in Fig. 3 and are 22225 rpm for the BM1/EO10/ND2 crossing, 27442 rpm for the BM1/EO8/ND4 and 36600 rpm for the BM1/EO6/ND6 respectively. At these speeds, the variations of aerodynamic damping with interlude phase angle (IBPA) were determined at the best efficiency operating points using the energy method according to Eq. 1.

$$\zeta_{aero} = \frac{-|W_{cycle}|}{2\pi E_{kin,max}} = \frac{-|W_{cycle}|}{8\pi^3 f^2 S_{CFD}^2} \quad (1)$$

The aerodynamic damping is determined from the aerodynamic work per cycle normalised by the kinetic energy of the modal vibration. When using mass-normalized eigenvectors, this energy equals to $(2\pi f)^2 * S_{CFD}^2$ where S_{CFD} is a scaling factor by which the blade displacement is scaled to a user-defined target value (here: 1% of the blade chord). The aerodynamic work per cycle in turn is determined from a projection of the complex blade forces onto the blade motion as shown in

FIGURE 3. SAFE diagram featuring the resonance speeds of the investigated resonance conditions

Eq. 2.

$$|W_{cycle}| = \pi \cdot f \int_{blade} |h| p (\vec{n} \cdot \vec{e}_h) dA \quad (2)$$

The resulting aerodynamic damping curves at the aforementioned operating conditions are depicted in Fig. 4. The damping curve of the highest rotational speed shows the smallest variation with interlude phase angle. It changes from the highest value of $9.65 \cdot 10^{-5}$ at an IBPA of 108° to the lowest value of $6.62 \cdot 10^{-5}$ at -95° . A reduction of rotational speed to 27442 rpm leads only to a moderate change in aerodynamic damping. In contrast to that, the highest change as well as the highest critical damping ratio can be observed at the lowest rotational speed. In this case, the value is changing from $17.74 \cdot 10^{-5}$ at -150° to $6.36 \cdot 10^{-5}$ at an IBPA of -20° . According to the SAFE diagram shown in Fig. 3, the EO10 excitation induces a backwards traveling wave mode at a nodal diameter of ND 2, which is equivalent to -60° . It is apparent that the aerodynamic damping at this IBPA is rather low, compared to other IBPAs. Since the ratio of maximum to minimum aerodynamic damping amounts to 2.79, this resonance condition is well suited to demonstrate the potential of using intentional mistuning to reduce resonant vibration amplitudes [11]. It is planned to demonstrate this reduction experimentally in an existing turbocharger test facility at the IKDG of the RWTH Aachen University (Esper et al. in [7]). The sections below focus on the design of an intentionally mistuned vane ring that induces the targeted EO10 excitation.

FIGURE 4. Variation of aerodynamic damping versus IBPA at different resonance speeds

METHODOLOGY FOR STATOR MISTUNING

Kovachev et al. [6] presented a study on the effect of vane ring mistuning due to random manufacturing-induced throat width variations. This variation induced several LEO excitations as derived from a spatial Fourier decomposition of the circumferential throat widths. This effect is used here in an targeted manner, by intentionally varying the throat width such that a given LEO excitation is obtained. To do so, the mean throat width is modulated by a sinusoidal variation at a given EO, as included in Eq. 3. There, variable dev stands for the maximum relative deviation from the mean throat width, while variable EO is set according to the targeted excitation order.

$$f(x) = \frac{dev[\%]}{100} \cdot mean\ throat \cdot \sin(EO \cdot r) + mean\ throat \quad (3)$$

Targeting an excitation order of EO10, Fig. 5 depicts the theoretical continuous throat width variation of a vane ring featuring an infinite number of vanes (blue dashed line) and one with a finite number of vanes (solid red line). An in-house tool is used to iteratively rotate each vane such that the intended throat width mistuning pattern is achieved while preserving the total throat width area. The resulting rotation angle of each vane are then used as an input to generate the full-annulus mesh of the mistuned vane ring using the mesh generation software NUMECA Autogrid 5 v 13.1. Subsequently, the full-stage CFD model including the volute, the mistuned vane ring, the rotor and the outlet is assembled using NUMECA IGG v13.1, as described above.

To validate the intentional mistuning method, a time-marching full-annulus simulation of the stage featuring the mistuned vane ring was carried out. The excitation orders induced by the vane ring are determined from a temporal Fourier

FIGURE 5. Exemplary throat width deviation for an intentional mistuning pattern of the stator vanes

FIGURE 6. Time-marching signal and harmonic spectrum of the pressure acting on the rotor blade

decomposition of the mean unsteady pressure acting on one rotor blade. Fig. 6 depicts the time-dependent pressure of one revolution as well as the corresponding harmonic contents. It is apparent that the EO equaling the number of vanes shows the greatest magnitude. Besides this, the effect of the intentional mistuning pattern is clearly visible, providing an excitation at the intended EO10 excitation order. Furthermore, a moderate peak is noticed at EO14, which stems from the difference of number of vanes (24) and the intentional mistuning pattern (EO10). The contributions at EO1 through EO3 stem from the asymmetrical shape of the inlet volute and are of subordinate importance.

ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT MISTUNING PATTERNS

In the following, the relation of the amount of mistuning and resulting vibration amplitude is assessed. Three mistuned vane rings are examined, each featuring the same throat width variation pattern while differing in mistuning strength. The first mistuned vane ring features a maximum throat width variation of 1.5% equalling the measured throat with variation of a previously tested randomly mistuned vane ring [6]. Two additional mistuned vane rings are analyzed, one featuring 2% and one 5% in maximum throat width variation. For each of these vane rings, a mistuned CFD model is created as described above and subject to unsteady CFD analyses using the NLH method focusing on EO10 and EO14. The results of these analyses are included in Fig. 7, showing the respective averaged harmonic blade surface pressures. While the harmonic mean pressure of EO10 at a deviation of 1.5% reaches 52.2 Pa it increases to 69.4 Pa at 2% and rises to 157.8 Pa at 5%. For EO14, the corresponding harmonic mean pressures are 27.8 Pa, 37.76 Pa and 91.87 Pa respectively. These results indicate that the harmonic pressure amplitudes increase monotonically with the amount of throat width mistuning. The last step is devoted to the forced response analysis at the target resonance condition. This anal-

FIGURE 7. Changing in harmonic pressure acting on the blade for different mistuning amplitudes

ysis follows the process described by Mayorca et al. [12], in which the distributed complex force vectors determined in the CFD analysis are mapped onto the FE model such as to perform a Forced Response Analysis (FRA) using a mode-superposition approach. The mapping is performed using an in-house tool, in which the CFD forces are mapped onto FE nodes using a weighing algorithm based on their distances to the closest nodes. The damping is extracted from the aerodynamic damping curve at the respective IBPA. To compare the excitations of the described patterns, the chord-wise tangential tip displacement obtained from the FRA is depicted in Fig. 8. In this chart, the blade leading edge (LE) is located at the origin of the chord length while the blade trailing edge (TE) is located at a chord length of 74.45 mm. The vibration amplitude increases from LE to TE, according to the investigated

FIGURE 8. Rotor blade tip displacement for different mistuning amplitudes resulting from forced response analysis

mode shape (BM1). It is apparent that the resulting blade vibration amplitude increases with increasing amount of throat width mistuning, which is in agreement to the effect on harmonic pressure amplitude as described above. It is concluded that the mistuning concept applied does not only allow to intentionally introduce a certain excitation order but also to accurately control the resulting blade vibration amplitude. The latter is of specific importance with regard to ensuring the mechanical integrity of the test object during testing.

TURBOCHARGER TEST RIG

For validation of the excitation due to the mistuned vane ring, the geometry of the designed stator is manufactured at the IKDG in Aachen. The validation measurements have been con-

FIGURE 9. Schematic test rig composition

ducted at the test stand which has been built up for the investigation in [8]. A six-stage high-pressure compressor is providing air with a maximum mass flow of up to 12 kg/s at 30 bara for the test bench, which is depicted in Fig. 9 schematically. The maximum inlet temperature for turbine investigation can be increased to a maximum of 500 °C by a 10.5 MW natural gas fired heat exchanger. Assisted by an electrical preheater, the inlet temperature can be controlled in a range of +/-1.0 K.

Besides the thermodynamic measurements of the operating condition, the excitation of the turbine structure is recorded at an inlet temperature of 500 °C by means of blade-tip-timing (BTT) measurements and strain gauge (SG) probes on the blade surface. Thereby, the positioning of the SGs follows the procedure described in [13] and [14]. Here, the three-dimensional strains and stresses of the investigated mode concluding from a FE modal analysis are transformed into a two-dimensional surface distribution with the corresponding angle of the main tension direction. Due to the test program, the SGs

FIGURE 10. Strain gauge position at suction side of a blade

are placed with respect to maximum strains and a minimum strain gradient to equally cover all examined modes. Resulting from this procedure, the placement of the SG can be described as seen in Fig. 10(b). Due to the limitation in the channels of the used telemetry, only eight high-temperature SGs could be distributed over the investigated wheel to study all modes and ND of interest. The used SGs have a resistance of 120Ω and they are connected via quarter bridge completion with a k-factor of 4.05. All of them are attached to the suction side of the blades as visible in Fig. 10(a).

Concerning the tip displacement measurements, the turbine housing is equipped with a total of eight non-equidistantly distributed laser-light sensors at the exducer plane, see Fig. 11(b). For this, the sensor locations are optimized for the investigation of the expected EOs and with regard to mounting accessibility. Each of the optical sensors has a head diameter of 1.7 mm and is flush-mounted with the housing wall. The

FIGURE 11. Blade tip timing in investigated turbine

emitted laser for the measurement has a wavelength of 450 nm and the intensity of each laser diode can be adjusted to get the best possible signal quality. An exemplary picture of the setup is depicted in Fig. 11(a). For the identification of the blades and to calculate the tip deflection, an additional once-per-rev signal is used. Hence, an optical sensor is attached through the compressor housing and generates its signal through an exciter on the shaft.

VALIDATION OF INTENTIONAL EXCITATION

First, the overall performance of the steady state simulation including the IGV with a maximum throat deviation of 5% (LEO10) is compared to the steady state results of the symmetrical vane ring (SD24) and the measurements (meas). The different colors in Fig. 12 show six different speed lines at each three specified boundary conditions. It can be seen that the performance map of the turbine can be well predicted by both of the numerical models. The deviation in the total-to-static pressure ratio compared to the measurements is in the range of 0.05% to 1.7%. Analysing the variation in mass flow, the difference from simulation to measurement is between 1.0% and 2.2%. Furthermore, the change of operating point due to the aerodynamically mistuning of the stator is negligible. There is no deviation in the operating point of the LEO10 model compared to the SD24 model at higher speeds and only a minor discrepancy in the pressure ratio is noticeable at the lowest speed.

Next, the normalized tip displacements of the BTT measurement are presented for various runs in Fig. 13. Here, each of the 12 blade tip vibrations are depicted in boxplots for a series of six measurements, three bottom-up and three top-down runs. The fact that all blades show a measurable tip deformation at the investigated frequency belonging to resonance of BM1 and EO10, validates the procedure of intentional excita-

FIGURE 12. Comparison of calculated and measured performance

tion described above. The range of the different displacement amplitudes lies between 0.22 and 0.98 with a mean value of 0.45. Furthermore, it can be seen that the rotor is structurally

FIGURE 13. Different measurements of tip displacement for each blade

mistuned which leads to a deviation of the maximum deflection of the examined mode shape of certain blades. Especially the blades enumerated with 3 and 10 show a significant deviation from the mean value over almost all runs. This mean value of the presented results will be compared to the displacement of the tip at the exducer plane as shown in Fig. 8. To do so, the boundary conditions from the measurements at resonance with BM1 have been used as an input for the forcing calculation and the vibration amplitude has been recalculated. The resulting

normalized amplitude at the exducer plane is 0.38 and leads to a deviation from measurement to simulation of 16.40%. Since the aim of the paper is the presentation of a way to intentionally induce a specific excitation pattern, the high amplitudes confirm the approach, which was taken in inducing LEO excitations.

Then, the normalized strain of the different SGs at the shown blades for the different measurements is presented in boxplots in Fig. 14. In comparison to the BTT measurements, not all items show an amplitude at the investigated frequency. The non-existing signal from the SGs at blade 8 and blade 11 can be explained by the failure of the probes during the setup. Nonetheless, the remaining sensors show a normalized strain at the examined resonance in a range from 0.22 to 0.85 with a normalized mean value of 0.46. Similar to the tip displacement, the blade enumerated with the number 3 shows a high amplitude which can be explained by the structural mistuning of the rotor. For the comparison with the strain from the FRA, the strains of the FE nodes which are covered by the imaginary SG position are averaged. The resulting normalized averaged strain from this calculation is 0.58 and leads to a deviation from measurement to calculation of -26.03%. Despite this deviation, the presented intentional excitation could be validated once more by the existence of the measurable strains at the investigated resonance at EO10 and BM1.

FIGURE 14. Different measurements of eight strain gauges at different blades

CONCLUSIONS

The paper aims to present a way to induce a specific excitation order to a radial turbine rotor by geometrical mistuning of

the upstream vane ring. In the first part, the investigated geometry and the associated numerical models are presented. Further, preliminary investigations have been carried out to motivate the used excitation pattern and the corresponding mode shape. The methodology for the mistuning is described afterwards. Based on a fully transient simulation including the mistuned stator, the workflow could be validated numerically. Following that, the influence of the mistuning amplitude is investigated with three different mistuning patterns. The result shows that the higher the maximum deviation of the throughflow area between two blades the higher the induced harmonic pressure on the blade and this results in a higher tip displacement in a subsequent forced response analysis. For validation of the numerical work, a stator with a maximum throughflow deviation of 5% is manufactured and examined on the test rig. The workflow is approved by means of BTT and SG measurements. The comparison of the calculated and measured values is summarized in Tab. 1. While the tip displacement from the calcula-

TABLE 1. Comparison of calculation and measurement

Result	Calculation	Measurement avg.	Deviation
Frequency	3704.2	3780.5	2.02%
Tip Disp.	0.3778	0.4519	16.40%
Strain at SG	0.576	0.457	-26.03%

tion is underpredicting the measured one, the strain from the FRA is overpredicting the value of the probes. Nonetheless, all investigated sensors show a measurable impact at the examined resonance condition validating the excitation and with this the presented workflow. Transferring the demonstrated intentionally excitation to other cases, certain LEO phenomena could be investigated in detail and with this, the knowledge of this type of forced response could be better understood.

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